

Fundamentals of Effective Management of the Pilgrimage Tourism Process

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ANNOTATION: Today, tourism serves as the main source of income of many developing countries. The export of tourism services creates an additional demand in the economy, providing employment to the population and increasing foreign currency revenue. Through this, the tourism sector plays an important role as the driving force for economic development. This article will talk about pilgrimage tourism, one of the currently rapidly developing types of Tourism, and the resources available in our country, and it will end with the conclusion of the authors.

KEYWORDS: pilgrimage tourism, pilgrimage, unique yogis, cultural heritage, tourism objects, Islamic religious yogis, Buddhism, Christian objects, steps, objects.

INTRODUCTION. Pilgrimage tourism is now a common tourism industry. Pilgrimage tourism is essentially the process of visiting shrines. Usually, pilgrimages organize long trips for religious purposes, which are carried out for days, weeks or even months. They are places where believers go to strengthen their relationship with their religion, including a whole journey. Pilgrimage tourism may include visiting mosques and churches in a city or specific area that can be visited, or other religious attractions. Pilgrimage tourism is a type of tourism that gives tourists a complete or strong motivation to achieve religious attitudes and Customs. This is not just a journey, it is an opportunity to realize your self, hope for spiritual purification, wish for the fulfillment of blessings and desires, a path to faith. Pilgrimage is-to appeal to the Almighty through the past Saints, to calm his mind and soul, to realize the truth of holiness, to go through the path of loneliness and purification. In Central Asia, this is called pilgrimage, which means visiting sacred places.

MAIN PART. Pilgrimage tourism is a set of trips of representatives of different religions for the purpose of pilgrimage. According to tradition, it refers to trips of religious purpose, but it may also refer to a secular sayokhat, which has achaeism in Alochi for the pilgrim. Pilgrimage tourism ethics can be based on two characteristics: how important pilgrimage tourism is for a shrine. How important is pilgrimage tourism for pilgrims? Pilgrimage can be an opportunity for many people to receive spiritual nourishment in difficult times. Human beings travel to certain destinations to make religious-secular Enlightenment known. Often long and sometimes difficult, sayokhat is an opportunity for people to think.

Rare yogis

Currently, one of the most important branches of international tourism is religious i.e. pilgrimage tourism. The history of the formation of pilgrimage tourism goes back to the distant past. That is, its first appearance dates back to antiquity. The main emerging resorts of pilgrimage tourism

are considered the homeland of the ancient Greeks and Romans. The ancient dagreks and Romans built temples and churches and worshipped them.

The main product of pilgrims' wanderlust is that the Dear Saint will take steps to places, mentally relieve himself in the midst of worship, purify the souls, be free from severe she would calciuean diseases, forgive God for the sin deeds he has poured, longing to be in spiritual closeness with his comrades during the journey. When visiting tourists go on their journey, they will enjoy achieving their dream, paying tribute to the creator in gratitude. To date, there are more than 10 major centers of pilgrimage tourism in the world, which are located almost in the co-ownership of the Earth.

There are also many places of pilgrimage in the Muslim world. In particular, in Central Asia, along with Jonajan Uzbekistan, there are incomparably many steps and places of pilgrimage where Dear Saints live and are buried. They include Akhmad Yassavi mausoleum in Turkestan, South Kazakhstan region; Zangiota complex in Zangiota district, Tashkent region; Sheikh Khivanda Taxur mausoleum in Tashkent City, Qaldirgoch-biya mausoleum, Yunuskhon mausoleum; Hazrati Imam complex; Abubakr Muhammad Kaffal Shashi mausoleum; Sheikh Zayniddin bobo mausoleum; Imam Al-Bukhari complex in Hartang village, Payariq district, Samarkand region; Mahtumi a'zam mausoleum in Dahbed Fort, Oqdarya district: Shahi Zinda in Samarkand City, Amir Temur, Ruhabad, Khoja Daniel, Motrudiy, Murod Aziz, Khoja Ahror Wali, White Palace, Chaybonota mausoleums; Bukhara city-Ismail Samani, Chashmai Ayub, Sadriddin Buharzi, Bohovuddin Naqshbandi, Boyan Kulikhan, Chor Akhror mausoleums; Three Saints in the Khorezm region, mausoleum of said Allovuddin; In the kashkadarya region-Jahangir, Dorus Saodat, Dorut Tilovat complex, blue dome mosque; in Surkhandarya region-Hakim at-Termiziy Complex; Sultan Saodat synagogue monument, Fayoztepa temple; in Jizzakh region-Sadr Vakhs saint (Saint) complex; in the Fergana region, such as the Dachman Shahan cemetery, Mozorikhan mausoleum are considered maskans that attract visiting tourists. You can get full information about Islamic monuments in Uzbekistan from Appendix 3. Among them is the city of Bukhara, called Bukharoyi-Sharif, which means blessed Bukhara in the Islamic world. Samarkand City with many priceless monuments. Considered the homeland of Amir Temur

City of Prince. Of course, these cities have an ancient and rich history and have undergone significant changes throughout their lives. The idea of eternity, eternity is associated with these cities. There is an incident in the biographies of the Prophet Muhammad. The Prophet prays. He had a heavenly horse, and he would ascend to heaven on that horse. First he visits Jerusalem and then Mecca. Looking at Mecca, he sees the sun's Rays illuminating the whole world. He then sees only two points on the surface of the earth, the Rays rising from the bottom to the top. These rays were Bukhara and Samarkand.

Christian objects

The emergence of Christianity in Central Asia is associated with the names of the apostles Foma and the first called Andrew, who were missionaries in the area in the early first millennium. Since then, the two most important religions in the world-Islam and Christianity-have lived peacefully together. There are more than 10 holy and revered Christian and Muslim places, shrines in Uzbekistan.

Until now, on the territory of Uzbekistan there are "Iowa Springs", which are revered by both Christians and Muslims, the most famous of which is located in Bukhara. Directly, the Orthodox Church in Uzbekistan began to form in Central Asia with the emergence of the Russian Orthodox Church, after the main part of this region was annexed to the Russian Empire and the establishment of the Turkestan governorate general (1867).

Buddhist heritage

In 1968, a Buddha statue was discovered in the ancient Termez area, and since that time the site

has become a major object of study by most archaeologists. Later, the oldest Buddhist temple complexes were opened: Fayoztepa (av. 1st century-3rd century AD), Campirtepa, Karatepa. The discovery of elements of the famous Ayritom frieze with the image of ancient musicians indicates that Buddhism was promoted on the territory of this region and elements of Hellenistic culture were revealed. Currently, terracotta bas-reliefs of the patterned border are kept at the State Hermitage in St. Petersburg. Have you ever thought about modern life, about the role of a person in it? Try to stop yourself even for a moment in pursuit of time. Take a break and think. What did the inner image of a person look like? Is it possible to call a modern person happy and what can make him happy? To find answers to such philosophical questions, someone devotes his whole life, others, unfortunately, cannot find the answer to these questions, while others go on a pilgrimage.

Opportunities for the development of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan is characterized by a wealth of tourist resources. Religious tourism in Uzbekistan is considered very rich in places of pilgrimage to St. kadjos. In particular, in Central Asia, along with jonajan Uzbekistan, there are incomparably many stepsons and pilgrimage sites where Dear Saints live and are buried. Many Saints' burial sites and graves are being renovated and restored to their original condition.

Among them, the mausoleums of such noble Saints and imams as Bahawiddin Naqshbandi, Ghijduwani, Imam al-Buhari, Mahtumi a'zam, Shohizinda, Motrudiy, Hakim at-Termiziy, Zangiota have been transformed into immeasurable, beautifully visited and spiritually inspired places of Muslim people. Of particular international importance is the transformation of the Imam Al-Bukhari complex into an important pilgrimage site. Because the shrine is the most important pilgrimage site in the Muslim world after the cities of Mecca and Medina.

Therefore, the creation of favorable conditions for visiting, that is, the formation of infrastructure linking, is an important issue of today. The main task here is to achieve the fact that citizens of foreign countries go on pilgrimage without excessive difficulties. For this, Samarkandshahri airport is the main solution to the issue, to be in line with the world's templates. During the years of independence, Religious steps are given great attention by the state. Due to the fact that our great ancestors paid serious attention to the restoration, improvement, repair of the places where the land was found, the shrine was built by maskans 1.5 billion. Attracts the Muslim world. Currently, serious attention should be paid to the territorial organization and development of religious tourism in our country. In particular, Southeast Asian and West Asian countries should develop activities in order to attract pilgrims. To do this, we consider it appropriate for the purpose of identifying, generalizing, creating religious tourist cards of the Republic and region and creating necessary conditions for pilgrims, building roads, studying transport opportunities, which are considered sacred by people in each region, district and village. There is no doubt that religious shrines will become a great source of income at the expense of low funds.

There are dozens, hundreds of religious steps from all regions of our country. But the routes of visiting them are not clearly drawn up. The sad state is that our selves, who served greatly in the Islamic world, rose to the rank of Saints, only know the abode they found in the eternal land at the local level, that is, in the district or regional miqiyya. Consequently, such holy shrines can be converted into religious shrine objects of the Republican and international level.

Now a common pilgrimage is the tourism sector. Pilgrimage tourism is essentially the process of visiting shrines. Usually, pilgrimages organize long trips for religious purposes, which are carried out for days, weeks or even months. They are places where believers go to strengthen their relationship with their religion, including a whole journey.

Pilgrimage tourism may include visiting mosques and churches or other religious attractions in

a city or specific area where visitors can visit pilgrimage tourism is a type of tourism that gives tourists a full or strong motivation to achieve religious attitudes and Customs.

Conclusion. Uzbekistan is considered one of the countries rich in Holy steps on a global scale. During the years of independence, the great thinkers who played an incomparable role in the development of Islamic science, or the study of the addresses found in the eternal land, their improvement was carried out, these addresses were transformed into places to visit. Such steps are considered sacred not only to the population of Uzbekistan, but also to the entire Islamic world. Currently, there are 1,851 objects of material and cultural heritage in the Samarkand region, while the number of them in the Bukhara region is 829. These include those that can be visited

The holy places are the majority.

In particular, among the facilities located in the Bukhara region alone, there are 105 mosques and 14 mausoleums, in which the opportunities for the development of pilgrimage tourism are considered high. These factors have served as the basis for the development of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan for the past four years, to bring it to the world level. But, nevertheless, there are issues in this regard that are waiting for their solution, the analysis of which can make it possible to develop some suggestions and recommendations on this matter. For this reason, scientific analysis of the work carried out in the field and their results is important.

In 2017, systematic work on the development and introduction of pilgrimage tourism, a separate area of tourism in Uzbekistan, was launched. In particular, on August 16, 2017, the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on the first-line measures for the development of the tourism sector in 2018-2019” was announced. This document approved the program of first-line measures for the development of the tourism sector in 2018-2019, aimed at easing travel to Uzbekistan, developing tourism infrastructures and establishing new tourist facilities.

In addition, within a month on the basis of this decision, it was established to form a list of countries in which special pilgrimage tourism programs are offered to their citizens from January 1, 2018 to simplify visa procedures, as well as to activate work on attracting tourists in the direction of pilgrimage tourism from Malaysia, Indonesia and other countries to the Holy steps in Uzbekistan. In addition, a new state standard was developed by the State Unitary Enterprise “Center for certification of tourist services” of the State Committee for the development of Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to facilitate visitors to our country. Tourist services from January 1, 2018 on the basis of this document,

The standard on the means of placement, general requirements has entered into force. According to the new rules, at least one-tenth of the total number of rooms in each hotel was prescribed with the condition that the Qur'an be placed karim, a place to pray, and a Qibla indicator at least 30 percent.

During this period, work was also carried out to ease the visa regime for tourists arriving in Uzbekistan. To this end, on February 3, 2018, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on additional organizational measures to create favorable conditions for the development of tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan” was published. In accordance with it, a visa-free regime was introduced for citizens of Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, Turkey, South Korea, Japan and Israel. A simplified visa procedure was also introduced for citizens of 39 countries. Foreigners entering without a visa were joined by Tajik people from March 2019, and French from October 2019. In addition, the state committee for the development of Tourism has developed maps of the development of pilgrimage tourism in the city of Tashkent, visits to 15 religious institutions registered. A map of halal dining areas, national cuisines, restaurants, family visits has been prepared, aimed at travel agencies and guests of Indonesia and Malaysia. Also, for the first time in our country, the “halal” standard was introduced, which is necessary for the field of pilgrimage tourism.

In conclusion, visiting tourism azal is a type of tourism that has long been shaped. Pilgrimage is inextricably linked to tourism, cultural tourism. Now every person needs to know his history and world history. This type of Tourism inspires people to emote, encourages a realistic view of life and makes everyone mature.

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